

ISic3538

Funerary epitaph for Alexion

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

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Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

unknown

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale
interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory A3550

Physical Description

Marble slab of which the lower right corner is lost

Dimensions

Height 32 cm

Width 32 cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 20 mm

Line 2: 30 mm

Line 3: 40 mm

Line 4: 35 mm

Line 5: 25 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: 40 mm

Interlineation line 2 to 5: 20 mm

Text

1. Θε (οῖς) · Χθο (νίους) ·
2. Ἀλεξίων · Ἰου
3. λίου · Σεβαστεῦς ·
4. ἐβίωσεν
5. ἔτη · μ [---]

Apparatus

text after I.Messina 33

Translation

Commentary

Ferrua suggests that Sebasteus is an ethnic ('from Sebaste', but which is unknown).

Digital identifiers:

TM 493871

EDCS 38200023

PHI 313665

Bibliography

Bitto, I. 2001. Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Messina. *Pelorias* 7. Messina. At 33

Ferrua, A 1941. *Analecta sicula. Epigraphica*. 3: 252-270. At 254-255 no.5

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